

RESPONSIBILITY OF COUNTRIES FOR EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATION ACTIVITIES IN THE FIELD OF DEVELOPMENT

Tashkhuzhaeva Gulnoza Saydamkhuzhaevna

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Annotation. Proposals are presented based on the experience of foreign countries on the development of innovative technologies in soybean cultivation.

Key words. Soybeans, innovations, innovative technologies, seeds, next generation soybeans. Chorian countries.

Every day, the role and importance of agriculture in ensuring food security of the world's population is increasing. Providing the population with agricultural products with rational use of the resources and opportunities available in our country, further increasing yields and fertility, processing of grown agricultural products. As a soybean bean plant, all crops are the best advanced for all types of winter grain crops, corn, corn, vegetable crops. Agriculture has the role and importance of a soybean plant. Shade is used for production in industrial enterprises, except for food products, soda, artificial fertilizers and medicines.

Therefore, in our country, great attention is paid to growing a soybean plant.

Seed production of grain crops in the United States has been transferred to an industrial base and created on the principle of narrow specialization. The mother continent of varieties is created mainly at agricultural experimental stations in the States, at research centers and at stations of the US Department of Agriculture. After receiving the maternal material, all subsequent work will be carried out by seed companies. About 600 seed production enterprises have been established, which are engaged in the cultivation, purification and pre-export processing of seeds, their supply to consumers and sale, as well as the production of seeds for export.

Seed companies are located in all regions of the country and specialize in the production of seeds of individual crops. They have a good material and technical base: an excellent economy of drying and cleaning seeds, highly automated warehouses, loading and unloading and transporting means, seed equipment. Firms enter into contracts with experienced farmers to grow seeds, advise them and introduce the most advanced technologies in growing seeds. Many private firms have their own technically well-equipped experimental stations, where scientists and seeds work.

The improvement of soybean varieties in China began in 1913, when the experimental agricultural station Gonchuling was created in the Jiling region and

began to form a local set of soybean varieties. The first soybean variety was created in 1923.

Since 1949, along with the development of agricultural technology for growing soybeans, research work on growing crops has been strengthened and developed. In 1956 and 1980, two large-scale operations were carried out, during which 15,000 and 10,000 samples of soy seed plasma were collected, respectively. Currently, the National Genetic Bank stores many samples of soy seed plasma, including varieties, natural varieties and annual wild shadows. This huge source of soy seed plasma is the basis for soy cultivation.

So, in 1949, more than 1,200 varieties of soybeans were created in China and more than a hundred research institutions engaged in growing crops were created. In recent years, seed companies have begun conducting research on soybean cultivation. The main way to improve soybean varieties is through transition, basic tribal image approaches, and individual choice.

Regional experiments with soybean varieties will be carried out in each region. At the state level, it can be divided into thirteen experimental groups depending on the peculiarities of their cultivation and ecological zones. After approval by the National Committee for the Study of Agricultural Varieties, new varieties will be created and used in production.

Improved varieties are characterized by high yields, resistance to diseases and stress resistance to abiotic factors. The quality of the facade has significantly improved. Most improved varieties are resistant to soybean mosaic virus, and spring soybean varieties in Northeast China are also resistant to bargosporosis. There are drought-resistant varieties, varieties with a protein content of more than 45% and a fat content of more than 23%. The increased content of isoflavones and the choice of non-inhibitive varieties of lipoxygenase and trypsin also allowed the development of improved varieties.

As for agricultural technology, depending on intensive agriculture, the methods of planting and using land have changed. For example, in the Northeast region, the "three knees" technique is used, where three main techniques are adopted in mechanized agricultural conditions: deep mitigation, layered agitation and spot planting in combination with chemical control of pests of weeds, diseases and insects. This allowed to increase soybean yield by 15-20%. Short-term varieties and seeded sowing also resulted in more than a 15% increase in yield.

Soy is the main oil in China and a source of protein for a healthy human diet. This plays an integral role in ensuring state grain reserves and product safety.

The climatic conditions of the entire Heihe County are favorable for the cultivation of locally zoned early baking varieties. They are distinguished by a short cold period and a combination of active air temperatures above + 10 °, which is 1600-2400} C. Precipitation is 500-600 mm per year. Soybeans are grown in the district.

Currently, Heihe County grows mainly soybeans using the following technologies:

1. The technology of growing soybeans 65 cm high, used in local farms and dekhkan yards, includes three operations:

- autumn tillage at a depth of 25-30 cm, which contributes to an increase in the temperature of the soil and the accumulation of moisture in it;
- fertilizers can be used in soil layers for digestion of feed substances by plants;
- spring planting is carried out with soil deepening to ensure harmony and uniformity of seedlings.

All three operations can be performed once a year (fall) or twice a year (fall and spring). Joint application of mineral fertilizers with trace elements is carried out based on the results of analysis of their soil content. For soybeans, mineral fertilizers N 20-30 kg/ha, P₂O₅ 50-70 kg/ha, K₂O-30 kg/ha are usually used, which are used at a distance from soils under seeds of more than 4-5 cm. Before planting, the soil is filled in and equals the fibers. Sowing from May 5 to May 15, when the soil is heated 10 ° C, the distance between them is 10-12 cm. The seeds are planted at a depth of 3-4 cm, the plant density should be 330-350 thousand times.

2. Technology for growing soybeans in two rows using the method of narrow-gauge crops. The distance between the ponds is 45 cm, the distance between the strips is 12 cm this technology is used in the mountain-cold zone, where the active temperature above + 10 ° C exceeds 2100°S. At the same time, high-performance pine varieties are used that are resistant to low-level, unfavorable living and environmental conditions. The parking density for me is 350-350 thousand times/year. In the fall, processing, cutting and breaking of the ridges will be carried out.

Deep softening with a depth of 12-15 cm with deep bathing or small bathing at a depth of 18-20 cm or with milling at 25 cm. Before planting, the seeds will be treated with medicines to combat diseases and pests. It is rational to apply shoots to soil layers in the following doses: H₂O-30kg/ha, P₂O₅ 60-80kg/g, Kcl 30-40kg/g, optimal planting time from May 5 to 15. 3-5 days after planting, herbicides are applied to the soil to destroy other people's herbs.

During the growth period, 2-3 crops will be carried out to combat soybean weed, as well as the purification of foreign rocks. Agitation with leaves during the flowering period. Soybeans are used during the growing season, when plants need sulfurous, fingers and deicing agents for chemical protection. Cleaning is done for a short time when soybeans ripen. These technologies are used as much as possible in large sites and are rapidly spreading in Heilongjiang province.

3. Technology for growing soybeans with increased density of plants used in Geihe government farms. Sowing is carried out in four rows on ridges 97.5 cm wide, 15-18 cm high from the brain, which go into three ridges with rows 65 cm; Plant six rows of narrow rows (distance between strips 15 cm) in ridges 130 cm high, turning into two ridges with rows 65 cm. In autumn, soil is treated, its surface is cut off and ridges are cut off.

Currently, in Heihe County, using the above technologies, the area of soybean cultivation is 400 thousand hectares, including broad knee technology - 10 thousand hectares, narrow circle technologies - 100 thousand hectares, soybean cultivation technology with a distance between ridges of 65 cm - 290 thousand hectares.

The administration of Heihe County pays great attention to the development of science and technology that contributes to the efficiency of soybean production due to its needs and needs among the country's population, which has been constantly growing in recent years.

Developed countries and rapidly developing European countries, the United States, China and Russia have accumulated rich experience in growing soybeans in agriculture. In these countries, the amount of funds allocated for research work in agriculture is increasing.

It is advisable to expand the scope of scientific research in the field of agriculture, to study and apply in practice the experience of opening scientific institutions in new areas of increasing the number of scientists.

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